

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B206
 Date: 4th Jun 2006
 Take Off: 09:33:38
 Landing: 14:50:58
 Flight Time: 5h17m20

Campaign: CLAPREC / NEON
Trials Instructions: Evora, coast nr Lisbon
Operating Area: Beja

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Roberts	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Ian Ramsay-Rae	Directflight
3	CCM	Gaynor Ottaway	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist	Dave Kindred	Met Office
5	Flight Manager	Steve Devereau	FAAM
6	ARIES	Joss Kent	Met Office
7	MARSS	James Bowles	Met Office
8	SWS	Ian Rule	Met Office
9	CVI	Jeff Brown	Met Office
10	Wet Neph	Andy Wilson	Met Office
11	Filters	Doug Anderson	FAAM
12	VPRACOP 1	Mario Reis	Instituto Tecnologico e Nuclear, Sacavem
13	AEROPOR 1	Frank Wagner	University of Evora
14	AEROPOR 2	Daniele Bortoli	University of Evora
15			
16			
17			
18			

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B206
 Date: 04 June 2006
 Project: CAPEX AERPOR VIPRACOP
 Location: Beja

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
----	----	-----	-----	---	-----
092435		Start-Up 4	0.44 kft	116	
092838		start taxi	0.44 kft	116	
093338		T/O	1.0 kft	184	
093729		JW zero	6.6 kft	186	
093752		Nevzorov zero	7.3 kft	186	
094240	095502	Profile 1	10.0 - 1.9 kft	344	
094746		change descent rate	4.9 kft	342	
095607		retract LBBR	1.9 kft	320	
100312	100710	Run 1.1	1.9 kft	123	
100939	101347	Run 1.2	1.9 kft	288	
101150		start H cal	1.8 kft	287	
101726	101930	Run 1.3	1.9 kft	109	
102213	102248	Orbit 1.1	1.9 kft	248	(aborted)
102331	102542	Orbit 1.2	2.0 - 1.8 kft	111	
102558	102808	Orbit 1.3	1.8 - 1.9 kft	118	
102930	103142	Orbit 1.4	1.9 - 1.8 kft	243	
103519	103917	Run 1.4	1.8 - 1.9 kft	295	
104034	104906	Profile 2	1.9 - 10.0 kft	090	
104118		LBBR extend	2.7 kft	097	
104457		interrupt profile 2	7.1 kft	097	
104621		restart profile 2	7.1 kft	260	
105546	110535	Profile 3	10.0 - 1.9 kft	293	
110122			3.9 kft	288	500ft/min
110623	110947	Profile 4	1.8 - 0.10 kft	284	
111224	112421	Profile 5	0.12 - 10.0 kft	083	
111619		int profile 5	3.9 kft	087	
111648		video	3.9 kft	023	change tapes
111739		recommence profile 5	3.9 kft	320	
113500	114439	Run 2.1	0.07 - 0.10 kft	164	
113733		retract BBR	0.08 kft	165	
114101		Heimann cal start	0.09 kft	174	
114604	115252	Profile 6	0.08 - 6.3 kft	315	start QNH 1022hPa
115259	115955	Run 3.1	6.3 kft	321	
115708		retract BBR	6.3 kft	321	
120200	120910	Run 3.2	6.3 kft	153	
121152	121533	Orbit 2.1	6.3 kft	137	
121620	122002	Orbit 2.2	6.3 kft	173	
122141	122241	Profile 7	6.3 - 7.3 kft	324	
122522	123223	Run 4.1	7.3 kft	166	
123541	124443	Run 4.2	7.3 kft	354	
124713	124828	Profile 8	7.3 - 8.3 kft	248	
124927	125627	Run 5.1	8.3 kft	188	
125536		Video	8.3 kft	188	change tapes
125946	130648	Run 5.2	8.3 kft	018	
130954	131423	Orbit 3.1	8.3 kft	191	

131537	131958	Orbit 3.2	8.3 kft	249
132232		Video stopped	12.3 kft	125 tapes stopped
133207	140313	Profile 9	15.0 - 0.54 kft	121
133200		interrupt Profile 9	14.1 kft	121
133349		restart videos	14.0 kft	120
133409		extend BBR	14.0 kft	121
133756		restart Profile 9	14.0 kft	121
133821		JW & nev zero	13.7 kft	124
134538		int profile 9	7.0 kft	122
134657		recommence profile 9	7.0 kft	004
135045		interrupt profile 9	3.9 kft	359
135149		recommence profile 9	3.8 kft	265
135425		interrupt profile 9	2.9 kft	259
135942		recommence profile 9	2.9 kft	184 QNH1018
140952	141452	Run 6.1	2.4 kft	061
141640	142139	Run 6.2	2.4 kft	244
142212	142735	Orbit 4.1	2.4 - 2.3 kft	299
142848	143116	Orbit 4.2	2.4 kft	022
143135	143230	Profile 10	2.4 - 3.4 kft	047
143250	143756	Run 7.1	3.4 kft	066
143757	143844	Profile 11	3.5 - 4.4 kft	069
144027	144529	Run 8.1	4.4 kft	246
145058		Land	0.51 kft	002 14 50 58
145617		Park posn	0.51 kft	107 38 05.13N 7 55.65W

B206 Track 04-JUN-06

SORTIE BRIEF

Flight No: B206
Date: 04/06/2006

Brief: 0830L
T/O: 1030L, Land 1530L

Programme: EUFAR (European Fleet for Airborne Research)
Project: CAPEX (Clouds and Aerosol over Portugal Experiment)

May/June 2006

SORTIE 1: Aerosols & clear skies (Mainly AEROPOR/VPACOP).

Conditions/Weather:

Ideally clear skies (some high cloud acceptable)

Trial Objectives:

To measure aerosol particles in differing vertical layer(s) from natural & anthropogenic sources.

Location:

Central/S. Portugal over land, or off W. Portugal coast (S of 40 deg N).

Flight Pattern:

1. Depart Beja and transit towards Evora at about FL100. (10min).
2. Profile descent from FL100 to lowest permitted height, at 1000ft/min (500 ft/min below FL 050), to finish overhead of ground-based site (including LIDAR) in central Evora, (20min).
3. Fly 2x S&L runs (each about 4 mins) at minimum permitted altitude to be overhead Evora ground station along part of run, ideally to be flown into and down sun, followed by series of 2 x orbits (about 30 deg bank) clockwise, at minimum permitted altitude. (30min).
4. Transit at medium level to another selected area - W. of Lisbon (near to Cabo da Roco), overflying Capa da Roco at minimum permitted altitude. Climb to FL100, and operate in either Capa da Roca restricted area (if possible), or in non-restricted area further to W of Lisbon (over water) for 5 & 6 below. (35 min).
5. Profile descent from FL 100 to lowest permitted altitude, at 1000 ft/min (500 ft/min below FL 050) in area of interest . (15 min).
6. For each layer of aerosol identified during the profile into the area the following runs will be flown at altitudes determined by the Mission Scientist. All altitude changes will be profiles. Runs to be oriented into or down sun.
 - (a) Fly two S&L 7-minute run 1000ft below aerosol layer (or minimum altitude if aerosol is close to ground/water) into and down sun, followed by series of 2 x orbits (about 30 deg bank) clockwise. (20 min).
(An extra run with SWS looking in the nadir may be flown to characterise the surface reflectance).
 - (b) Series of 7 min straight and level runs in the aerosol layer to characterise microphysics of plume. Number will depend on thickness of layer. (15 min).
 - (c) Fly two S&L reciprocal runs, 1000ft above the aerosol layer, each 7 minutes, into and down sun angle, followed by series of 2 x orbits (about 30 deg bank) clockwise. (An additional run with SWS looking in nadir may be flown). (20 min).

7. Transit at medium/high level to another selected area around Beja, and repeat 5 (but from FL150) and 6 above, as time allows. (115 mins).
8. Recover to Beja. (20 mins).

(Total time: 5h 00 m).

DRK
03/06/2006

Notes:

1. EVORA LIDAR: In centre of town; approx 4 km N. of Evora airfield. La: 38 deg 34 ' 04" N, Lo: 07 deg 54'43" W. Elevation: 293 m.
2. CAPA DA ROCA: CIMEL Sun photometer ground site. La: 38 deg 46'58" N, Lo 09 deg 30'00" W.
Altitude: 140 m.

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST DEBRIEFING SHEET

Date: 04/06/06. Flight number: B206

CAPEX Detachment, Beja. AEROPOR (Type 1) sortie. (To measure aerosol particles in differing vertical layers from natural & anthropogenic sources).

Overall, a very successful flight.

Firstly, horizontal runs and orbits were made close to Evora ground lidar site (in centre of town, operated by Evora University). After overflying Cabo da Roca (coastal CIMEL sun photometer site) at minimum permitted altitude, vertical stack patterns were then made (a) in Restricted areas R42A,B just West of Lisbon (overwater), then finally over and around the local Beja area.

Cloud Physics PCASP was unavailable for this flight (undergoing change of laser), but the CVI PCASP worked well. ARIES suffered a software problem for about the first hour of flight, but thereafter OK; no other instrument problems were reported. A good dataset therefore, with SWS/SHIMS, MARSS (including channel 16), CVI, and Wet Neph working particularly well. Filter samples for the VPRACOP group were taken through the sortie. A co-ordinated approach for viewing angles for SWS and ARIES (also for HEIMAN - see instrument logs) was operated throughout.

Weather conditions were almost ideal. No cloud initially was present, but about 2-3/8 thin Cirrus slowly invaded the maritime operating area from the west during the flight. Otherwise no medium or low cloud was present. Winds were light at all levels, mainly SE'ly. Visibility was good throughout. The main aerosol/pollution layers were in general much more pronounced visually (verified from instruments, mainly CVI), over land compared to over the water.

After T/O from Beja at 0934Z on Runway 19, we were quickly into our first profile descent from FL100, at 1000 ft/min, reducing to 500 ft/min below 5000 ft, to finish overhead Evora Lidar. Two S&L 4-minute runs, and one 2-minute run were made into sun and downsun, at 2000 ft, WNW – ESE, with Evora Lidar at the E end of these. This was followed by 3 clockwise orbits (at 2000 ft, following the current solar zenith angle in terms of bank angle) centred to NW of Evora, finishing with a 4-minute S&L run, starting o/h Evora and running WNW, away from sun.

Next, we profiled (P2) from 2000 ft to FL100, initially towards Evora, then heading W towards Lisbon. Tops of the pollution layer here was about 8500 ft. We then made a profile descent (P3), from FL100 to finish o/h Cabo da Roca at lowest permitted altitude at 2000 ft at 1000 ft/min, but changing to 500 ft/min below 5000 ft. Profiles P4 and P5 combined meant we climbed from 50 ft to 250 ft (P3), then from 250 ft to FL100 (P4) in the area near Cabo da Roca to investigate the temp/moisture/aerosol/pollution structure. From the resultant tephigram, the main (marine) inversion/hydrolapse was at 7250 ft, so chosen levels to work here were 6250 ft (below), 7250 ft (in) and 8250 ft (above) the main aerosol layer.

A S&L run to characterise the sea surface was made at 250 ft (about 10 mins), followed by a profile ascent to 6250 ft. A series of runs (R3.1, R3.2) into & down sun, and orbits (O2.1, O2.2) were made at 6250 ft, then climbing to 7250 ft (P7). Runs into and down sun at 7250 ft (R4.1, R4.2) were made in this pollution layer. After climbing to 8250 ft (P8), Runs 5.1 & 5.2 were made into & down sun, followed by Orbits 3.1 & 3.2 at about 17 deg solar zenith angle.

After this, we climbed to FL150 and transited back via o/h Lisbon to Beja, and profiled down into the base area (P9) from initially FL150, then from FL 140, at 1000 ft/min, changing rate to 500 ft/min at 5000 ft, all the way down to 50 ft as a missed approach. From the information gathered during P9, we decided on a main pollution layer, centred at 3500 ft. S&L runs were therefore made at 1000 ft below (R6.1 & 6.2), into and down sun, at 2500 ft, with Orbits O4.1 & O4.2 to follow, a profile ascent to 3500 ft (P10), with a single S&L down sun run made at

this height, (Run 7.1), a profile ascent to 4500 ft as P11 at 1000 ft/min, followed by a final single S&L run at 4500 ft as R8.1.

After quickly getting all gear suitably stowed for landing, we landed at Beja at 1551z, after a busy, but successful, sortie lasting 5h 17m.

DRK

06/06/06

CORE CHEMISTRY FLIGHT LOG FOR FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight Number : B206

Date : 04/06/06

Operator and contact info : Kate Turnbull katet@faam.ac.uk

Problems with Instruments

CO	None
O₃	None
NO_x	Ozonator flow low (< 0.02 lpm) at FL100 and above.
SO₂	N/A
TDLAS	N/A
WAS	N/A

N.B. The PI requested that Core Chemistry run automatically. Therefore, what actually happened during the flights is not known but it is assumed that the problem with the NO_x analyser noted on B204 was also a potential problem during B205.

Mission Scientist's Log

Aerobor (Orbiter - Type ①)

Flight No **B206**.....

Date **04/06/2006**.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
0923		→			QTH = 1019 mb (BEJA).
0924		→			Engine start up.
0929		→			Start TAXI; T/O Q/W 19 (TOS) (2) Nil cloud (SKC). Good surface vis (>15km)
0933					
0933					T/O BEJA. Climb to FL100 (heading S).
0935	Climb out.	Passing 4000' (1019)	190°		
0941					Haze/Aerosol tops ~ 8500/9000' (coincident with inversion)
0942	START P1	10.0kft.	343°	37° 54' N 7° 54' W	Start P1 Wind 075° / 3m/sec
0947	P1	5.0kft	342°	38° 06' N 8° 0' W	Haze/Aerosol top 8500/9000'. Change descent rate to 500'/min
0953	P1	3.0kft	346°	38° 24' N 07° 54' W	SKC Wind 140° / 4m/sec
0954			→		Passing Evora Airfield (to Sthd) ahead.
0955	P1-1	1.8kft	044°	38° 30' N 07° 48' W	End P1 (Lider - Evora) Manoeuvring to start downsun run
1003	START R1-1	1.8kft	107°	3'	Start R1-1 (at 2000' 1019 mb) (Turn)
1007	END R1-1	1.9kft	104°	38° 30' N 7° 48' W	Into sun, finishing o/h EVORA LIDAR End R1-1 Wind 170° / 05 m/sec
1009	START R1-2	1.8kft	285°	(Turning R) 38° 30' N 07° 48' W	Manoeuvring to start downsun run next Start R1-2 o/h Evora (2000' 1019 mb)
1011				(Slight gear)	Wind 103° / 3m/sec. Temp = +20.6°C DPT = +19.6°C
1013	END R1-2	1.8kft	286°	38° 36' N 8° 12' W	End R1-2. Turning for 2 min run back towards
1017	START R1-3	1.8kft	112°	38° 30' N 8° 0' W	Start R1-3 into sun, towards Evora.
1019	END R1-3	1.8kft	112°	38° 30' N 7° 48' W	End R1-3 } Manoeuvre, before (starting 2x orbits)
1022	START orbit 1	1.8kft	241°	—	Start } going 9/clockwise in orbit
1022	END orbit 1	—	—	—	End orbit } will RE-DO THIS ORBIT!

ADVIS SW PROBLEMS

Mission Scientist's Log

R 42A
R 42B
3100'
2000'
Cap. In
back

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Date **4/6/06**.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
102231	orbit 1.2	1.7 kft	145°	38° 30' N 75° 4' W	Start orbit 1.2 (CLOCKWISE THIS TIME) (Sol. zen angle 32°)
102542	orbit 1.2	1.8 kft			End orbit 1.2.
102559	orbit 1.3	1.8 kft			Start orbit 1.3
102808	orbit 1.3	1.8 kft		38° 30' N 75° 4' W	End orbit 1.3 } will do another orbit for SVS. Maneuver for n/min.
102930	START orbit 1.4	1.8 kft	250°		Start orbit 1.4 (offset to SW from orbit 1.2/1.3).
103142	orbit 1.4	1.8 kft		38° 30' N 80° 0' W	End orbit 1.4.
103450					will finish by being final run to end (4 min) o/a EVORA to exit EVORA area
103519	START orbit 1.4	1.8 kft	295°	38° 30' N 75° 4' W	Start orbit 1.4. (AWAY FROM SW)
103748					Passing Lake/Reservoir to Sthd. Winds 110° / 4 m/sec [5/10 kts] not clear.
103917	orbit 1.4	1.8 kft		38° 36' N 80° 12' W	End orbit 1.4
104034	START P2	2.0 kft	095°		Start Profile P2, 2000' ↑ 10000'. towards EVORA, then leave area.
1041	Passing	3200'			aircrew change to 1013 Alt. setting.
104457	WIND	7.1 kft			Interrupt P2 & turning ← before complete P2 to FL100.
104621	RESUME P2	7.2 kft	258°		Resume P2. (FROM T/O.)
104740		8500'			Top of haze/poll ² layer here (CVI & visually). SKE, apart from Trace Ci to WSW.
104906	END P2	10.0 kft	252°	38° 30' N 80° 00' W	End P2 Transit → LISBON → CABA DA ROCA
105546	START P3	10.0 kft	285°	38° 30' N 80° 42' W	Start P3 ↓ 1000' / min
105710		8.8 kft			Set to 1019 QNH now
105924					Change to 500' / min Passing LISBON o/h mouth of estuary now.

110200 →

Mission Scientist's Log

Message

6550'
 6550'
 6550'
 6550'

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Date **4/6/06**.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
110530			←		o/h Capa da Rocca NW (as close as we can pass)
110535	END P3	1.8kft			End P3
110623	START P4	1.8kft	287°	38° 42' N 9° 36' W	Start P4 to 50' over water (down NW of Capa da Rocca)
110947	END P4	250'	294°	38° 41' N 9° 48' W	End P4 at 250'
					Turning ↻ before climbing to FL100. to investigate Marie Br.
111224	START P5	250'	083°	38° 42' N 9° 48' W	Start P5, towards Capa, will turn ↻ at 400' & then resume climb to FL100 heading NW
1115		3100'			Good inversion/isothermal layer top here.
111625	Interrupt P5	3.8kft			Interrupt P5 just shy of coast: SKC except for 1/5 CI to NW
111739	Restart P5	3.8kft			Restart P5 ↗ 1000'/min CVI counts here ~ 1/2 of over land (some ship exhaust seen low level) Inversion/hydrolysis here, visual haze top here (also fewer counts above on CVI).
112421	END P5	10.0kft	322°	39° 12' N 9° 54' W	End P5. Will descend to 250' & perform 7 min run to characterize S. surface
113500	START 2.1	250'	164°	39° 12' N 9° 45' W	Start R2.1 at 250'. (characterize sea surface).
1136			→		Wind 19C/surface 210/15kt (forecast) Hazy here, below inversion.
114142		330			Climb (insect/bird avoidance)
114240					↳ again here. Staying off coast (Capa da Rocca)
114439	END 2.1	300'	172°	39° 42' N 9° 30' W	End R2.1 then Profile ↗ 1000'/min to 6250' (1000 mb)
114604	START P6	300'	318°		Profile P6 ↗

Mission Scientist's Log

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SOLAR
AZIMUTH
144°

A₂ = 181°

A₂ = 153°

A₂ = 167°

A₂ → 174°

A₂ = 178°

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
115252	END 6 START 3.1	6.3 kft	321°	39° 0' N 9° 54' W	End P6 / Start R3.1 at 6250'. (7 min run) Wind 125° / 2 m/sec.
115955	END R3.1	6.3 kft		39° 24' N 10° 15' W	End 3.1. Turning onto reciprocal. for next 7 min run [Haze pollution layer less pronounced above as we go further from coast]
120200	START R3.2	6.3 kft	153°	39° 15' N 10° 18' W	Start into sun run (UNDER AGL 2000 L1/SL 1000 below) 2/8 thin Ci (to SW) otherwise SKC
1208.					Wind 309° / 3 m/sec.
120910	END R3.2	6.2 kft	0	38° 54' N 10° 00' W	End R3.2 at 6250'.
1210	ABORT				Start Orbit 2.1, abort (SWS not ready) start again shortly
121152	START 2.1	6.3 kft	171°	39° 0' N 9° 54' W	Start Orbit 2.1 About 28 miles from photometer site for this orbit
121543	END 2.1	6.3 kft	156°		End Orbit 2.1
121620	START 02.2	6.3 kft		38° 54' N 9° 54' W	Start Orbit 2.2. Thicker Haze / Pollution over land.
122002	END 02.2	6.3 kft		38° 54' N 9° 54' W	End Orbit 2.2. Manoeuvre then climb to 7250'.
122141					Start P7
122241	END P7	7.2 kft	325°		End P7 at 7250'.
122522	START A.1	7.3 kft	169°	39° 00' N 10° 00' W	Start R4.1 at 7250' in aerosol layer. Little visual evidence of pollution here but starts over coast & inland significantly 3/8 Ci (to 5 mainly)
123233	END R4.1	7.2 kft		38° 30' N 9° 48' W	End R4.1 Manoeuvre for SWS to prepare for next run.
123541	START R4.2	7.2 kft			Start R4.2
124443	END R4.2	7.2 kft	340°	39° 18' N 9° 48' W	End R4.2. Wind 125° / 1 m/sec
124713	START P8	7.2	245°		Climb to above aerosol layer 8250'. Start P8 climb to 8250'

Mission Scientist's Log

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
124828	END P8	8250'			End P8
124937	START RS-1	8250'	187°	39° 6' N 10° 6' W	Start RS-1 into SW.
125635	END RS-1	8250'			End RS-1 Turn onto reciprocal downwind
					SWS crashed out, need ~2 mi to recover.
125946	START S-2	8250'	077°	38° 48' N 10° 10' W	Start RS-2 downwind.
					WIND 145° / 16 m/sec.
					CI to W, clear over land
					Thicker Haze/Pollution "hugging land" / locked onto land surface.
130648	END RS-2	8250'		39° 12' N 9° 48' W	End S-2
130954	START O3-1	8:31kft	2	39° 6' N 9° 42' W	Start Orbit 3.1 (17° SLAT AZ.)
					Some CI now between sea level on these orbits.
131423	END O3-1	8:31kft			End O3.1
131537	START O3-2	8:31kft	257°	39° 0' N 9° 48' W	Start Orbit 3.2.
131959	END O3-2	8:31kft		39° 0' N 9° 48' W	End Orbit 3.2. Climb towards FL150 & transit to Beja for last stack pattern.
1324		→			Up to FL 150 now
132535		→			O/h coast now (6 miles N. of Cabo da Roca).
P9 descent	FL150 ~ FL140				PASSING O/H LISBON AT FL150.
133620	TRANSIT TO BEJA	14.0kft	121°	38° 24' N 8° 30' W	Start descent FL140 ↓ towards BEJA
133756	DEPART P9	14.0kft	118°		Recommence P9, 27 miles from BEJA.
					Good Haze/Pollution layer ahead.
					Beja QNH = 1019 mb.
					Small inversion/iso at 10500! Haze/Pollution Top visibility 9000'.
134538	P9 Intercept				Intercept P9 turn ↻
					Will finish P9 o/h Beja at 50'

Az 20187°

Az 20196°

N1330

(missed approach)

Mission Scientist's Log

CLEAR ABOVE

240°

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
134657	P9	7.0kft	003°	38° 06' N 7° 48' W	Recommence P9
1348					Dew Pt. varying rapidly 5500' to 6500'.
134943		5.0kft			Change descent rate to 500'/min
135045	Interp P9	3.8kft			Intercept P9, turn ↖
135149					Recommence P9
135425	Interp P9	2.8kft (3000' ENH)			Intercept P9 (1019), chg
135642					changing to 1018 local ONH now
135942	Recomm P9	2.8kft (3000' ENH)			Recommence P9 Approaching Beja from N.
140312	END P9		183°	38° 00' N 7° 54' W	o/h threshold Beja 50' End P9 Climb to 2500' 4500'
					Will work 3500' (M.W. LATER) 2500'
140952	START R6.1	2.3kft	063°	37° 50' N 8° 00' W	Start R6.1, downward.
141255					Beja to PRT.
141452	END R6.1				End R6.1
141640	START R6.2	2.4kft	243°	38° 00' N 7° 48' W	Start R6.2 into Sun
141430					Passing above Beja to start
142139	END R6.2	2.4kft			End R6.2. Thin Ci slowly increasing from W (in distance)
142212	ORBIT 4.1				Start Orbit 4.1
142					Re-start Orbit 4.1 (Extend orbit to ~1/2 times for SWS.)
142735	END ORBIT 4.1	2.3kft		38° 54' N 8° 12' W	End orbit 4.1
142850	START ORBIT 4.2	2.3kft			Start orbit 4.2
143106					End orbit 4.2
143135	START P10				Start P10 2500' / 3500'.
143230	END P10				End P10.
143250					Start Dawson W. 7.1 at 3500'.

242°

247°

Filter Sampling Log

Flight No:

B206

Date:

4 Jun 2006

Operator:

Mario / Doug

Type of filters mounted in	Top inlet	90mm diameter types AC, PC & P	Bottom inlet	90mm diameter types AC, PC & P
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Run No	Disk #1 TOP	Disk #2 MIDDLE	Disk #3 BOTTOM	Inlet Top/ Bottom	Time On	Time Off	Flight Run	Accum Vol [l]	Comments
Filters run 1	AC37	-	-	Top	10:03:28	10:19:34	R1.1/2/3	940	1900' R1.1 10:03:28-10:07:10 (into sun) R1.2 10:19:39, R1.3 10:17:26-10:19:30
Filters run 1	AC38	-	-	Bottom	10:03:28	10:19:34	R1.1/2/3	1290	
Filters run 2	PC15	-	-	Top	11:35:00	11:44:40	R2.1	732	250' above sea level towards Cabo da Roco R2.1 1 11:35:00- 11:44:39
Filters run 2	PC16	-	-	Bottom	11:35:00	11:44:40	R2.1	1007	
Filters run 3	PC17	-	-	Top	11:52:57	12:10:55	R3.1/2	1687	6300' (over sea, below aerosol layer)
Filters run 3	PC18	-	-	Bottom	11:52:57	12:10:55	R3.1/2	2307	
Filters run 4	PC19	-	-	Top	12:23:21	12:44:43	R4.1/2	2334	7300' (over sea, in aerosol layer)
Filters run 4	PC20	-	-	Bottom	12:23:21	12:44:43	R4.1/2	2169	
Filters run 5	P11	-	-	Top	12:48:38	13:06:48	R5.1/2	2534	8300' (over sea, above aerosol layer) Both filters loose at end of run
Filters run 5	P12	-	-	Bottom	12:48:38	13:06:48	R5.1/2	3158	
Filters run 6	AC39	-	-	Top	13:23:	13:32:45	transit	637	FL150 (Transit to Beja area) Top filter broke
Filters run 6	AC40	-	-	Bottom	13:23:	13:32:45	transit	898	
Filters run 7	P13	-	-	Top	14:10:04	14:21:42	R6.1/2	1067	2500' (under haze layer)
Filters run 7	P14	-	-	Bottom	14:10:04	14:21:42	R6.1/2	1134	2500' (under haze layer)
Filters run 8	PC21	-	-	Top	14:32:47	14:37:51	R7.1	664	3500' (in haze layer)
Filters run 8	PC22	-	-	Bottom	14:32:47	14:37:51	R7.1	819	3500' (in haze layer)
Filters run 9	PC23	-	-	Top	14:39:19	14:45:29	R8.1	577	4500' (above haze layer)
Filters run 9	PC24	-	-	Bottom	14:39:19	14:45:29	R8.1	759	4500' (above haze layer)

ARIES flight log

Flight: B206

Location: BEDA, Portugal

page 1 of

Date: 4/06/06

Operator(s): Joss Kern

Resolution: 1

Gain A: 2 B: 2

Notes:

on ground

DRS time	Flight ptrn	Filename	Shttr	HBB	CBB	Mir.	Det.	Win	Macro(s)	Comments
093338	T/O	—	120 scans	nan	ok	→	until 0955	low level		
			ARIES coming up with "Flight-ID requires Scharseiers" when trying to run a Macro. Reloaded all software but still a problem. In the end changing disk from G: to H: did the job. Don't know why!							
			All working ok now though							
105305	Transit	B206E	clsd				HBB @	52.6°C	—	will reset to 70°C.
113121	Prep for	B206F	clsd	70.9	31.4	22.9	-190.6	34.0	CH1 x 2	Cal before run start
113500	R2.1	B206G	clsd	70.8	30.7	23.3	-190.6		N1 x 2	
113622	R2.1	B206H	clsd					33.4	N1 x 3	
113809	R2.1	B206I	open	70.6	31.1	24.6	-190.6	32.6	Z1 x 2	Quick zenith view.
113925	R2.1	B206J	clsd	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	CH1 x 2	
114041	R2.1	B206K	clsd	71.0	31.6	24.9	-190.6	32.6	N1 x 3	
114302	R2.1	B206L	clsd						N1 x 2	
114414	R2.1	B206M	clsd	71.0	31.3	25.1	-190.6	32.6	CH1 x 2	
115137	Prep for	B206N	clsd	70.6	31.2	25.9	-189.9	33.8	CH1 x 2	
115252	R3.1	B206O	open						Z1 x 5.	
115537	R3.1	B206P	clsd						N1 x 2	
115656	R3.1	B206Q	clsd	70.9	31.8	23.9	-190.6	31.9	Z1 x 2 CH1 x 2	
115869	R3.1	B206R	open						Z1 x 2	
115941	R3.1	B206S	clsd	70.9	31.8	22.6	-189.9	31.1	CH1 x 2	

ARIES flight log

Flight: B206

Location: Pomeje, off Lisbon

page 2 of

Date: 4/19/06

Operator(s): JSS

Resolution: 2

Gain A: 2

B: 2

Notes:

DRS time	Flight ptrn	Filename	Shttr	HBB	CBB	Mir.	Det.	Win	Macro(s)	Comments
120202	R3.2	B206T	open	70.0	31.9	22.7	-190.6	31.9	Z1 x 5	
120440	R3.2	B206U	closed	71.52	31.9	21.7	-190.9	30.5	CH1 x 2	
120555	R3.2	B206V	open	70.7	32.0	21.9	-189.9	30.9	Z1 x 4	
120820	R3.2	B206W	closed						N1 x 2	
120944	R3.2 end	B206X	closed	71.0	31.8	21.1	-189.9	30.4	CH1	Overran run slightly
122249	R7 end	B206Y	closed	71.0	31.0	21.4	-190.6	32.7	CH1	end of run start.
122529	R4-1	B206Z	open	70.7	31.1	20.4	-190.6	32.0	Z1 x 5	
122805	R4-1	B206	closed	71.1	31.5	19.9	-190.6	29.7	CH1 x 2	
122924	R4-1	B2061	open						Z1 x 4	
123132	R4-1	B2062	closed						N1 x 2	
123246	R4 end	B2063	closed	71.0	30.8	20.0	-190.6	29.8	CH1 x 2	
123519	R4-2 start	B2064	closed	71.0	31.1	20.2	-190.6	30.2	CH1 x 2	Recovered software just run ^{running} prob
123634	" "	B2065	open	70.5					Z1 x 4	
123947	" "	B2066	closed						CH1 x 2	
124001	" "	B2067	closed	70.9	31.7	20.1	-190.6	30.2	N1 x 4	
124346	" "	B2068	open	70.8	30.6	20.2	-190.6	30.2	CH1 x 2	
124346	" "	B2069	open	70.5	31.7	20.2	-190.6	29.4	Z1 x 2	
124500	" "	C206A	closed	71.2	31.0	19.6	-190.6	29.4	CH1 x 2	
124818		C206B	closed	70.9	31.0	20.0	-190.6	30.8	CH1 x 2	

ARIES flight log

Flight: B206

Location: Pennycuik off 103km

page 3 of

Date: 4/6/66

Operator(s): Joss.

Resolution: 2

Gain A: 2 B: 2

Notes:

DRS time	Flight ptrn	Filename	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Mir.	Det.	Win	Macro(s)	Comments
124936	RS-1	C206C	std	709	310	20.1	-190.6	30.8	N1 x 5	
125216	RS-1	C206D	clsd	710	314	19.7	-190.6	30.2	CH1	
125344	RS-1	C206E	open	706					Z1 x 5	
125930	RS-1 end	C206F	clsd	710	310	19.2	-190.6	29.2	CH1 CH1 x 2	
130047	RS-2	C206G	clsd						N1 x 5	
130321	RS-2	C206H	clsd	709	314	18.9	-190.6	29.3	CH1 x 2	
130434	RS-2	C206I	open						Z1 x 4	Crrows e end of run.
130651	RS-2	C206J	clsd	704	315	18.8	-190.6	27.9	CH1 x 2	
140535		C206K	clsd	708	309	22.8	-189.9	30.6	CH1 x 2	
140819		C206L	clsd	711	309	23.7	-189.9	30.8	CH1 x 2	
141602	R6-1	C206M	open						Z1 x 5	
141245	R6-1	C206N	clsd	705	324	27.9	-190.6	30.9	Glew 3 x 4	
141355	R6-1	C206O	open						Z1 x 2	
141513	R6-1	C206P	clsd	711	34.8	28.7	-190.6	30	CH1 x 2	
141702	R6-2	C206Q	clsd						Glew 3 x 4	
141815	R6-2	C206R	clsd						Glew 3 x 4	
141936	R6-2	C206S	open						Z1 x 4	shutter closed 25mm
142026	R6-2	C206T	open						Z1 Z1 x 4	

Microwave Radiometers FLIGHT LOG	Date	04/06/06	Flight	B206	log pages
Operator(s)	JB	Campaign	CAPEX		
Departure	Beja	Arrival	Beja		

**System start
MARSS**

Visual pod inspection					•
Close 3 SSP circuit breakers					•
Close all MARSS circuit breakers					•
FERA on			at time	07:08:35	
Temperature controller initial temps	Ch16	20°C	Ch 17	20°C	Ch18 19.6°C
Temperature controller set points		54°C		58°C	-20 40°C
MARSS CPU on			at time	07:12:50	
Initial target temperatures	Hot	290.3	Cold	291.1	
Target heating					•
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***					•
Scanning on (LMD box)			at time	07:14:26	
Scan indication		Monitor	•	Visual	•

Deimos

Close all Deimos circuit breakers	Not Fitted			
Turn on Deimos CPU				
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***				
Start Deimos Software			at time	
Initial target temperatures	Hot		Cold	
Target heating				
Scan indication		Monitor		Visual
Weather	Cloud	none	Precip	None
	Surface	dry	Pressure	1019
	Other			

System functionality check (after initial system warmup, approx 1 hour)

PC to DRS Time error	$t_{PC}=t_{DRS} +$	0	at time	07:15:00
Brightness temps 'sensible'				•
Target temps	MARSS:	Hot		Cold
	Deimos:	Hot		Cold
Channel gains 'sensible'	Ch1 A (-)	Ch3 A (-)	Ch1 B (-)	Ch3 B (-)
	Ch16 (40-44)	Ch17 (45-49)	Ch18 (40-44)	Ch19 (40-44)
	43.5	34.1	38.49	40.66
				Ch20 (44-48)
				41.8

Power changeover

Headset on before start		•
Listen to engine start sequence	4, 3, 2, 1.	•
LMD off (3 switches, bottom to top)		•
Exit Deimos Software (x)		
POWER CHANGEOVER		
LMD on (3 switches, top to bottom)	then pushbutton	•
Restart Deimos Software		
System running again		at time

Wet Nephelometer Log

 Flight No **B.206**

 Date 04/06/2006

 Operator's name: Wilson

 Page 1 of 5

GMT	Run	Height	Sample flow	Dry neph RH	Wet neph RH	Temp ramp	T _{water}	Remarks
093908		—	11.0	3.1	34	—	22	Data start
094240	P1	FL100*	12.2	3.1	34	—	22	
094300			12.2	3.1	34	↗	22	set water to 41°C
094645	P1	060	12.3	17.4	65	↗	40	
095430	P1	2000ft	14	35	72	↗	40	set to 43°C
095502	P1	2000ft	13.5	40	77	→	43	end P1 @ 2000ft
095954	Positioning	2000ft	13.6	39	81	↘	43	set to +11°C
100312	R1.1	2000ft	13.8	44	66	↘	29	start R1.1 into Sun & over EVOA LIDAR site
100710	R1.1	2000ft	13.5	42	52	↘	19	end R1.1.
100910	Positioning	—	13.7	43	48	—	14	set to +4°C
100939	R1.2	2000ft	13.7	42.5	51	↗	31	Start R1.2
101347	R1.2	2000ft	13.4	43	85	—	44	end R1.2 - scattering increases by 40% with a doubling of humidity.
101726	R1.3	2000ft	13.5	44	88	—	44	start R1.3
101930	R1.3	2000ft	13.5	43	88	—	44	end R1.3
102059				44	88	↘	44	set to +6°C
102213								
102331	Orbit 1.2	2000	13.7	46	69	↘	28	start orbit 1.2 (orbit 1.1 abandoned - wrong direction)
102542	1.2	2000ft	13.7	41	61	↘	23	
102559	1.3	—	13.6	41	58	↘	21	start orbit 1.3 (30° AOB)
102808	1.3	—	13.6	42	54	↘	19	end orbit 1.3

Wet Nephelometer Log

 Flight No **B206**.....

 Date 04/06/06.....

 Operator's name: Wilson.....

 Page 2 of 5...

GMT	Run	Height	Sample flow	Dry neph RH	Wet neph RH	Temp ramp	T _{water}	Remarks
102930	orbit 1.4	2000ft	13.5	42	51	↗	16	set temp to +44. Start orbit 1.4
103142	1.4	---	13.8	43	69	↗	42	end orbit 1.4
1034				42	84	—	44	Aerosol shows marked growth at 70% RH (30% growth)
103519	R1.4	2000ft	13.6	40	85	—	44	start R1.4
103917	R1.4	---	13.5	42.5	87	—	44	end R1.4
104044	P2	2000ft ↗	13.5	41	87	—	44	start P2 → FL100
104906	P2	FL100	12.1	1.1	81	—	44	end P2 @ FL100
105311	transit	FL100	11.9	1.8	77	↘	44	set temp to +11C
105546	P3	100 ft	13.1	0	44	↘	23	start P3 → 250ft.
110100	.	400ft	13.8	21	38	↘	16	
110225		3000ft	14.2	18	35	↗	15	set water temp to +43C
110535	P3	2000ft	13.9	21	70	—	43	end P3.
110623	P4	--- ↘	14.00	21	73	—	43	start P4 → 250ft over sea.
110947	P4	250ft		60	86	—	45	end P4
111224	P5	250ft ↗	13.2	58	87	↘	45	end P4 start P5 to FL100. set to +41C
111619	P5	400ft	12.4	22	78	—	41	int P5
111739		400ft		21	78			re start P5. set to +45C
112421	P5	FL100	11.9	1	83	—	45	end P5 @ FL100
112730			12.4	0	82			set to +5C
113130	descent	2500ft	12.3	20	56	↘	25	

Wet Nephelometer Log

 Flight No **B206**.....

 Date 04/06/06.....

 Operator's name: Wilson.....

 Page 3 of 5.....

GMT	Run	Height	Sample flow	Dry neph RH	Wet neph RH	Temp ramp	T _{water}	Remarks
113500	R2.1	250ft	13.2	50	51	↗	18	Start R2.1. 250ft over sea nr Capo de Roca.
113530		250ft	13.2	64	55	↗	18	set to 45C
114140			13.7	60	87	↘	42	set to +5c.
114439	2.1	250ft	13.7	61	68	→	25	end R2.1.
114604	P6	250ft ↗	13.8	64	66	↘	23	start P6 → FLO63
115752	P6/P3.1	FLO63	12.4	18	34	↗	18	end P6, start R6 ^{3.1} . Set temp to +45c.
115600	R3.1	063	12.2	15	68	↗	44	
115955	3.1	063	14.0	11	78	—	45	end R3.1
120200	R3.2	063	14.1	15	71	↘	42	start R3.2. Set temp to +15. into Sun sun.
120910	R3.2	063	13.8	18	33	→	15	end R3.2.
121152	orbit 2.1	063	14	16.8	33.1	↗	15	start orbit 2.1. 30 AOB clockwise. Set temp to +43
121534	orbit 2.1	063	14.2	15.5	70.5	↗	42	end orbit 2.1
121620	orbit 2.2	063	14.1	17	72	→	43	start orbit 2.2
122141	P7	063 ↗						start P7 ↗ FLO73
122241	P7	073						end P7. set to +45c.
122522	R4.1	073	11.8	5.4	83	→	45	start R4.1
122810	R4.1	073	11.9	0.8	82	↘	45	set to +7c.
	R4.1	"	"	1	42	→	21	end R4.1
123541	R4.2	073	12.1	1.5	33	↘	16	Start R4.2
123705	"	"	12.1	2	29	↗	15	set to 45c

Wet Nephelometer Log

 Flight No **B.206**.....

 Date 04/06/06.....

 Operator's name: Wilson.....

 Page 4 of 5.....

GMT	Run	Height	Sample flow	Dry neph RH	Wet neph RH	Temp ramp	T _{water}	Remarks
124443	4.2	073	13.4	2.8	76.3	—	44	end 4.2
124713	P8	073	13.2	0	63	↘	44	Start P8. Set water temp to +6C
124828	P8	083	12.8	0	54	↘	29	end P8.
124927	5.1	083						
125627	5.1	083						
125946	5.2	083	13.0	0	22	↗	13	Start R5.2, Set water to +45C.
130648	5.2	083	11.2	0	66	—	39	
130954	orbit 3.1	083	11.2	0	68	—	39	Start orbit 3.1
131423	3.1	083	11.3	0	69	—	39	end orbit 3.1
131537	orbit 3.2	"	11.3	0	70	—	39	Start orbit 3.1
131958	3.2	"	"	"	69	—	39	end 3.1
132000								climbing to FL150 for transit to Seja. 25 mins (ish)
133207	P9	150						start P9
133257		140						int P9
133756	P9	140						restart P9 + set water to +43C
134538		070	13.5	12	82	—	43	int P9
134657	P9	070	14.1	14	83	—	43	Restart P9
135045		4000ft	12.9	32	89	—	43	int P9
135149		"						Restart P9
135425	P9	3000ft	13.5	39	91	—	43	int P9

Wet Nephelometer Log

 Flight No **B206**.....

 Date 04/06/2006.....

 Operator's name: Wilson.....

 Page 5 of 5.....

GMT	Run	Height	Sample flow	Dry neph RH	Wet neph RH	Temp ramp	T _{water}	Remarks
135844	P9	3000ft	13.0	35	90	↓	43	set to +40c
135942	P9	-"-	13.0	35	86	-	40	re start profile.
140315	P9	500ft	12.9	37	85	-	40	end P9 at 500ft over Beja airfield
140530				38	84	↓	40	set to +5C
140952	R6.1	2500ft	13.9	41	63	→	20	set to +43, Start R6.1 5 min runs.
141452	L.1	-"-	13.7	37	88	-	43	end R6.1
1416	R6.2	2500ft	13.7	37	88	-	43	start R6.2 - <i>Brumby</i>
141750	-"-	-"-	13.7	35	86	↓	43	set to +6C - <i>ramping down</i>
142131	L.2	-"-	13.8	40	62	↓	22	end R6.2
142	orbit 4.1	-"-	13.7	39	55	↓	18	start orbit 4.1
142739	4.1	-"-	13.7	37	46	↓	12	end orbit 4.1
142850	4.2	-"-	13.6	39	44	↓		start orbit 4.2
142848	4.2	-"-	13.7	39	41	→	9	end orbit 4.2
143135	P10	2500ft ↑	13.7	39	60	↓	9	start P10 → 3500ft
143230	P10	3500ft		34	44	→	9	end P10
143250	R7.1	3500ft	13.3	34	44	→	9	start R7.1 set water to +44c
143756	R7.1/P11	3"-	12.4	31	81	→	43	end R7.1 / start P11
143844	P11	4500ft	14.5	31	82	-	43	end P11
144037	R8.1	4500ft	14.4	29	82	-	43	start R8.1
145740								Data stop on Ground.

SWS and SHIMS FLIGHT LOG SHEET

Flight #	B206	Date	4/6/06	Operat or(s)	Ian Rule	log page	1	of	3
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Note to operator: Indicate whether entry refers to SWS or SHIMS

Time	Run id	Alt/FL	Mirr Pos	Int Times		Remarks	S W S	U S H	L S H
				Vis	NIR				

0715						Set time on rack pc, 'about time' not working?			
0716						Set time on laptop (only half second fast)			
092743						Start video count = 0:00:00			
093340						Take off Beja			
094240	P1	FL100	Zen + 6	200	500	Start profile			
0945			shims	50	200			x	
095503		2000' qnh				End profile			
100313	R1.1		Zen + 6 to start , then various	200	500	Item 3 on brief, view started with Zen + 6 then scanning fore or aft (depending on position of sun) by approx 10 deg for approx 30 each position			
100710						End run			
100939	R1.2		Zen + 6 to start , then various			Item 3 on brief, view started with Zen + 6 then scanning fore or aft (depending on position of sun) by approx 10 deg for approx 30 each position			
101347						End run			
101726	R1.3	2000' qnh	Nad - 6	200	500	Start run			
101930						End run			
102213	O1.1	2000' qnh	Zen + 6	200	500	Start orbit anti clockwise			
102248						End			
102331	O1.2			200	500	Orbit clockwise			
102542						End			
102600	O1.3			200	500	Orbit clockwise			
102810						End			
102931	O1.4			50	200	Orbit clockwise			
103141						End			
103520	R1.4	2000' qnh	Zen + 6 then various	50	200	Down sun run, sws scanning as before			
103917						End run			
104035	P2	2000' qnh	Zen + 6	100	200	Start profile			
1042			shims	50	200	Zero cal for shims			
104909		FL100				End profile			
105546	P3	FL100	Zen + 6	100	200	Start profile			
110538						End profile			
110623	P4	2000'				Start profile			
110946		250'				End profile over sea			
111221	P5	250'	Zen + 6	100	200	Start profile			
112424		FL100				End profile			

SWS and SHIMS FLIGHT LOG SHEET

Flight #	B206	Date	4/6/06	Operat or(s)	Ian Rule	log page	2	of	3
Note to operator: Indicate whether entry refers to SWS or SHIMS									
Time	Run id	Alt/FL	Mirr Pos	Int Times		Remarks	S W S	U S H	L S H
				Vis	NIR				

113501	R2.1	250'	Nad - 6	200	500	Start run over sea			
114439						End run			
114604	P6					Start profile			
						End profile			
115255	R3.1	6300'	Zen + 6 plus various	100	200	Start run, item 6b, down sun			
115955						End run			
120202	R3.2	FL063	Zen + 6 plus various	100	200	Start run item 6b, into sun run			
120910						End run			
121152	O2.1		Zen + 6	100	200	Start orbit clockwise			
121535						End orbit			
121620	O2.2		Zen + 6	15	15	Start orbit clockwise			
122002						End orbit			
122143	P7		Zen + 6	100	200	Start profile			
122242						End profile			
122523	R4.1	7300'	Zen + 6 plus various	100	200	Start run, item 6b, into sun run			
123223						End run			
123315						Stop tape count = 3:04:51			
123435						Start tape count = 0:00:00			
123543	R4.2	7300	Nad - 6	100	200	Start run, item 6b, sws missed beginning of run			
124443						End run			
124715	P8	7300	Zen + 6	100	200	Start profile			
124826						End profile			
124927	R5.1	8300	Zen + 6 plus various	100	200	Start run, item 6b, into sun			
125628						End run, sws modules dropped out			
125945	R5.2	8300	Nad - 6	100	200	Start run, item 6b, down sun, sws back on, sws nir dropped out			
130648						End run			
130955	O3.1	8300	Zen + 6	100	200	Start orbit clockwise			
131425						End orbit			
131537	O3.2	8300	Zen + 6	15	15	Start orbit clockwise			
131958						End orbit			
133202	P9	FL150	Zen + 6	100	200	Start profile, sws nir dropped out, ok now			
1338			shims	30	200	ok			
140317		50' agl				End profile			
120955	R6.1	2500'	Zen + 6 plus various	100	200	Start run, item 6, down sun run			
144042						End run			
141641	R6.2	2500'	Nad - 6			Start run, item 6, into sun			
142141						End run			
1422?	O4.1	2500'	Zen + 6	100	200	Orbit, missed recording start on Zen			

Flight Manager's Instrument Status Log

Flight No. **B** 206 Date: 4th June 2006

Instrument	Operated	Instrument	Operated
<u>Navigation</u>		<u>Cloud Physics</u>	
INU	Y	Probes	
XR5M GPS	Y	FFSSP	N
Cruciform GPS	Y	PCASP	N
Satcom C	Y	2D-P	N
Satcom H	Y	2D-C	N
<u>Thermometers</u>		Cloudscope	N
De-Iced Temp	Y	SID 1	N
Non De-Iced	Y	SID 2	N
Heimann	Y	HVPS	N
<u>Hygrometers</u>		CIP25	N
G. Eastern	Y	CIP100	N
J. Williams	Y		
Nevzorov	Y		
TWC	N	Racks:	
FWVS	N	INC	N
<u>Radiometers</u>		CCN / CPC	N/Y
Upper Clear	Y	CVI	Y
" Red	Y	(CVI includes PCASP)	
" Silicon	Y		
" SHIMS	Y	<u>Aerosol</u>	
Lower Clear	Y	PSAP	Y
" Red	Y	Nephelometer	Y
" Silicon	Y	Filters	Y
		AMS	N
<u>Large Radiometers</u>			
IR Camera	N		
TAFTS	N	Others:	
MARSS	Y	AVAPS	N
DEIMOS	N	IR Camera	N
ARIES	Y	NIR TDLAS	N
SWS	Y	2BT O3	N
<u>Chemistry</u>		VACC	N
Ozone	Y	PEROXIDE	N
SO2	N	Formaldehyde	N
NOX	Y	ADA	N
CO	Y	CPI	N
ORAC	N	Noxy	N
PAN	N	PTRMS	N
PERCA	N	Bag Sampling	N
WAS	N	Tube Sampling	N

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B206

Date: 4th June 2006

Instruments

1. SATCOM-C reports "system clock error in CMOS clock." Turn-around message received in pre-flight check.
2. PCASP fault prevented use this flight. Laser replaced on ground and PCASP returned to service post-flight

Aircraft

Large amount of insect debris on FFC

Satcom Calls

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B206:

Log	Reason
CVI	No log is ever taken for CVI

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

3 x Forward Facing Cameras
3 x Downward Facing Cameras

Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with :

Dave Kindred

EU Aircraft Liaison Officer
Observations Based Research
Jupiter Wing J-M-W014
Met Office
FitzRoy Road
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AFWA LPFR-NE MM5 15Km

RH(>70%) BARBS(KT)TEMP(C) FL Visibility (statue miles)

VALID:12Z04JUN2006

ICING **LGT** **MDT** **SVR**

LPFR **Notes:** Wind direction is relative to a compass (barbs to left indicate westerly wind), not relative to route of flight. Start point is always on left side of cross section, endpoint on right hand side. Model terrain drawn per route of flight. **NE**

AFWA LPST-SE MM5 15Km

RH(>70%) BARBS(KT)TEMP(C) FL Visibility (statue miles)

VALID:12Z04JUN2006

ICING **LGT** **MDT** **SVR**

LPST

Note: Wind direction is relative to a compass (barbs to left indicate westerly wind), not relative to route of flight. Start point is always on left side of cross section, endpoint on right hand side. Model terrain drawn per route of flight.

SE

BEJA,

AFWA MM5 Output

1 1.5

	Pressure	Height	W Dir	W Speed
(SPC)->	997	687	105	9
	975	1332	105	13
	950	2069	105	14
	925	2816	105	15
	900	3561	105	16
	875	4361	100	16
	850	5158	100	17
	800	6808	85	17
	750	8557	95	18
	700	10411	95	15
	650	12382	80	14
	600	14488	75	13
	550	16743	75	9
	500	19161	70	4
	450	21776	50	1
	400	24621	275	1
	350	27753	270	5
	300	31263	290	8
	250	35239	305	12
	200	39934	305	18
	150	45828	310	19
	100	54077	305	11

Lid Strength Index = 3.74209
 Thickness 1000mb - 500mb = 5655m
 Thickness 1000mb - 850mb = 1386m
 SWEAT = 114
 Environ. Helicity = -11
 Storm Rel. Helicity = -8

CAPE = 0
 K Index = 3
 Total Totals = 40
 Lifted Index = 5
 Convective Inhibition = 0
 Max UWV = 0.01 at 100mb
 Mean Rel Humid 1000-500mb = 38%
 Lapse Rate 850mb - 500mb = 5.29C/Km
 Lapse Rate 700mb - 500mb = 6.4C/Km
 Lapse Rate 700mb - 400mb = 7.03C/Km
 Precipitable Water = 0.75in
 036 HR FCST SKEW-T
 12Z 04-JUN-2006

GRID PNT LAT = 38.15 LON = -7.68
 STATION LAT = 38.016 LON = -7.866

SAGRES

AFWA MM5 Output 1 1.5

Pressure	Height	W Dir	W Speed
(SPC) -> 1020	0	100	20
1000	579	100	27
975	1292	100	30
950	2016	95	31
925	2758	95	32
900	3519	95	32
875	4300	95	30
850	5104	95	26
800	6767	90	20
750	8525	90	16
700	10388	90	14
650	12368	95	12
600	14477	90	8
550	16734	80	6
500	19158	75	4
450	21774	105	2
400	24628	175	2
350	27767	250	4
300	31272	300	10
250	35278	315	21
200	39990	310	30
150	45885	300	25
100	54116	290	11

Lid Strength Index = 6.3527
 Thickness 1000mb - 500mb = 5663m
 Thickness 1000mb - 850mb = 1378m
 SWEAT = 69
 Environ. Helicity = -31
 Storm Rel. Helicity = -31

 CAPE = 0
 K Index = -8
 Total Totals = 37
 Lifted Index = 6
 Convective Inhibition = 0
 Max UW = 0.0198123 at 100mb
 Mean Rel Humid 1000-500mb = 30%
 Lapse Rate 850mb - 500mb = 5.82C/Km
 Lapse Rate 700mb - 500mb = 6.83C/Km
 Lapse Rate 700mb - 400mb = 7.23C/Km
 Precipitable Water = 0.66in
 036 HR FCST SKEW-T
 12Z 04-JUN-2006
 CL
 GRID PNT LAT = 36.815 LON = -8.638
 STATION LAT = 37 LON = -8.983

AFWA MM5 Output 1 1.5

	Pressure	Height	W Dir	W Speed
(SPC) ->	1020	50	175	5
	1000	624	160	9
	975	1341	150	11
	950	2073	145	13
	925	2818	140	13
	900	3562	140	13
	875	4363	135	13
	850	5160	125	11
	800	6820	110	8
	750	8568	105	11
	700	10422	110	13
	650	12393	100	11
	600	14499	85	11
	550	16752	75	9
	500	19171	85	8
	450	21782	130	3
	400	24626	200	3
	350	27753	235	5
	300	31250	275	8
	250	35243	305	15
	200	39942	305	23
	150	45826	300	21
	100	54085	290	7

Lid Strength Index = 3.23243
 Thickness 1000mb - 500mb = 5654m
 Thickness 1000mb - 850mb = 1383m
 SWEAT = 111
 Environ. Helicity = -30
 Storm Rel. Helicity = -24

 CAPE = 0
 K Index = 7
 Total Totals = 42
 Lifted Index = 4
 Convective Inhibition = 0
 Max UW = 0.01 at 100mb
 Mean Rel Humid 1000-500mb = 43%
 Lapse Rate 850mb - 500mb = 5.64C/Km
 Lapse Rate 700mb - 500mb = 6.41C/Km
 Lapse Rate 700mb - 400mb = 7.1C/Km
 Precipitable Water = 0.93in
 036 HR FCST SKEW-T
 12Z 04-JUN-2006

 GRID PNT LAT = 38.04 LON = -9.596
 STATION LAT = 38.866 LON = -9.4

VORA

AFWA MM5 Output 1 1.5

	Pressure	Height	W Dir	W Speed
(SPC)->	994	765	110	7
	975	1342	110	10
	950	2078	110	11
	925	2828	110	12
	900	3592	110	13
	875	4373	110	13
	850	5170	105	14
	800	6820	85	13
	750	8565	85	17
	700	10416	100	14
	650	12390	80	13
	600	14493	70	13
	550	16744	70	9
	500	19163	60	5
	450	21776	20	1
	400	24622	275	3
	350	27751	275	6
	300	31249	295	8
	250	35231	305	12
	200	39922	305	16
	150	45816	310	17
	100	54066	305	11

Lid Strength Index = 2.86411
 Thickness 1000mb - 500mb = 5663m
 Thickness 1000mb - 850mb = 1387m
 SWEAT = 127
 Environ. Helicity = -6
 Storm Rel. Helicity = -4

 CAPE = 0
 K Index = 4
 Total Totals = 42
 Lifted Index = 4
 Convective Inhibition = 0
 Max UVW = 0.00711067 at 400mb
 Mean Rel Humid 1000-500mb = 40%
 Lapse Rate 850mb - 500mb = 5.30C/Km
 Lapse Rate 700mb - 500mb = 6.43C/Km
 Lapse Rate 700mb - 400mb = 7.06C/Km
 Precipitable Water = 0.81in
 036 HR FCST SKEW-T
 12Z 04-JUN-2006

 GRID PNT LAT = 38.595 LON = -7.68
 STATION LAT = 38.566 LON = -7.9